

Group of p-th roots of unity modulo n

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Abstract—Let $n \geq 3$ be an integer and p be a prime odd number. Let us consider $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ the subgroup of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ defined by :

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \{x \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^* / x^p = 1\}.$$

In this paper, we give an algorithm that computes a generating set of this subgroup.

Keywords—Group, p-th roots, modulo, unity.

I. INTRODUCTION

LET $n \geq 3$ be an integer, recall that $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ denotes the group of units of the ring $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})$. For more details on the structure of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ see [2], [3] and [4]. The group $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ has several applications, the most important is cryptography, that is RSA cryptosystem (see [7]). The security of the RSA cryptosystem is based on the problem of factoring large integers and the task of finding e -th roots modulo a composite number n whose factors are not known.

Let p be a prime odd number, we notice by $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ the part of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ formed by the elements x that verify $x^p = 1$. We can easily prove that $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is a subgroup of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ which contains exactly the unity and the elements of order p . Remember also that these elements of order p in $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ exist if and only if p divides $\lambda(n)$, with λ is the Carmichael lambda function, otherwise $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is not reduced to $\{1\}$ if and only if p divides $\lambda(n)$. The elements of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ other than 1 have the order p and so the order of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is of the form p^t with t an integer. Then we obtain the following result:

Proposition :

Let $n \geq 3$ be an integer and p be a prime number, then there exists an integer t such as :

$$\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p(n)) = p^t$$

with $t = 0$ if and only if p does not divide $\lambda(n)$.

Our work consists to determine explicitly the integer t described in the preceding proposition and by giving at the same time with an effective manner the decomposition of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ in product of cyclic groups and give a generating family of this group. Finally, we give the algorithm written in Maple. The case $p = 2$ is treated in [1] and in this article, our approach is the same as it. For more details about the algorithmic number theory see [5] and [6], and for introduction to Maple see [10].

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II. P-TH ROOTS OF UNITY MODULO N

Let us consider an integer $n \geq 3$ and p a prime odd number, let $n = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ the decomposition of n in prime factors.

We know that the p-th roots of unity modulo n , which are nontrivial, exist if and only if p divides $\lambda(n)$, that is to say $\alpha \geq 2$ or there exists i such as p divides $p_i - 1$.

Thus, in our study, we will distinguish these following cases $\alpha = 0$, $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha \geq 2$, but before that we are going to give some results which will be useful thereafter.

Definition 2.1: Let $n \geq 3$ be an integer and p be a prime number, we denote $\alpha_p(n)$ the number of prime factors q of n such that p divides $q - 1$.

Remark :

- $\alpha_2(n)$ is the number of prime odd factors of n .
- The function α_p is additive, that is to say if n and m are coprime numbers, then

$$\alpha_p(m.n) = \alpha_p(m) + \alpha_p(n)$$

and generally, for all the numbers not equal to 0, n and m we have:

$$\alpha_p(m.n) = \alpha_p(m) + \alpha_p(n) - \alpha_p(\text{GCD}(m, n)).$$

In the following, we consider an integer $n \geq 3$ whose the factorization is $n = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$, with p a prime odd number dividing $\lambda(n)$.

Proposition 2.1: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n . If p does not divide $p_i - 1$, then p_i divides $x - 1$.

Proof :

We have $x^p \equiv 1[n] \implies x^p \equiv 1[p_i]$ and thus the order of x in $(\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^*$ is 1 or p , but the order of x in $(\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^*$ divides $p_i - 1$ and thus it cannot be p . Therefore $x \equiv 1[p_i]$ and then we obtain the result. ■

Now, we will ameliorate the precedent result with the following lemma :

Lemma 2.1:

$$\text{GCD}(x - 1, 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1}) \in \{1, p\}$$

Proof :

One can easily verify that we have:

$$(x - 1)(x^{p-2} + 2x^{p-3} + 3x^{p-4} + \dots + (p - 2)x + (p - 1)) - (1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1}) = p. \blacksquare$$

Corollary 2.1: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n . If p does not divide $p_i - 1$ and $p \neq p_i$, then $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides $x - 1$.

Proof :

We have $x^p \equiv 1[n] \implies x^p \equiv 1[p_i^{\alpha_i}]$ then $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides $x^p - 1 = (x - 1)(1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1})$, or p does not divide $p_i - 1$ and thus p_i divides $x - 1$ also we know that the $GCD(x - 1, 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1}) \in \{1, p\}$ and $p \neq p_i$, then $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides $x - 1$. ■

If p divides n , that is to say $\alpha \geq 1$, and x is a p -th root of unity modulo n , then p divides $x^p - 1 = (x - 1)(1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1})$ and consequently p divides $x - 1$ or $1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1}$ and seeing the relation given in the proof of *Lemma 2.1* we conclude that p divides both at the same time, and thus

$$PGCD(x - 1, 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1}) = p.$$

We are interested now in the case of $\alpha \geq 2$, we saw in [1] for $p = 2$ that $2^{\alpha-1}$ divides $x - 1$ or $x + 1$, we are going to see that this result is not true for an odd prime p and more precisely we have the following result:

Proposition 2.2: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n ($\alpha \geq 2$), then $p^{\alpha-1}$ divides $x - 1$.

The case $\alpha = 2$ is trivial, for $\alpha \geq 3$, one needs the following lemma:

Lemma 2.2: Let p be a prime odd number and x be an integer, then we have :

$$x^p \equiv 1 [p^3] \implies x \equiv 1 [p^2]$$

Proof :

It is clear that $x^p \equiv 1 [p^3] \implies x \equiv 1 [p]$, so $x = 1 + kp$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}$) and consequently $x^p \equiv 1 + p^2k [p^3]$ (this writing is possible because $p \geq 3$) moreover p^3 divides p^2k , then p divides k and finally we obtain: $x \equiv 1 [p^2]$. ■

Remark : Notice that the precedent lemma is not true for $p = 2$, for instance $3^2 \equiv 1 [8]$ and $3 \not\equiv 1 [4]$.

Proof of Proposition 2.2:

We have $x^p \equiv 1 [p^\alpha]$ ($\alpha \geq 3$) and so in particular $x^p \equiv 1 [p^3]$, from the precedent lemma we conclude that $x \equiv 1 [p^2]$.

We have p^α divides $x^p - 1 = (x - 1)(1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1})$ and as $PGCD(x - 1, 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1}) = p$ besides p^2 divides $x - 1$, so $p^{\alpha-1}$ divides $x - 1$. ■

Remark :

The precedent proposition shows that $p^{\alpha-1}$ divides $x - 1$, but this does not mean that the p -adic valuation of $x - 1$ is $\alpha - 1$ and this is proved by the following examples.

An application example :

• $n = 7^3 * 29 = 9947$, we have $344^7 \equiv 1 [n]$ and $344 \equiv 1 [7^3]$. $2402^7 \equiv 1 [n]$ and $2402 \equiv 1 [7^4]$.

• $n = 7^2 * 29 * 43 * 71 = 4338313$, we have $350547^7 \equiv 1 [n]$ and $350547 \equiv 1 [7^4]$.

Let us return to our principal aim, which is the study of the group $G_p(n)$, we begin by the case $\alpha = 0$.

Case 1 : $\alpha = 0$

Let n be an integer whose decomposition into prime factors is $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with $p_i \neq p$ for all i . Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , we have shown in the above results that if p does not divide $p_i - 1$, then $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides $x - 1$. The condition p divides $\lambda(n)$ implies that it exists at least an integer i such that p divides $p_i - 1$, let σ be a permutation of the set $\{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ such that $n = p_{\sigma(1)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(1)}} p_{\sigma(2)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(2)}} \dots p_{\sigma(d)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(d)}} p_{\sigma(d+1)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(d+1)}} \dots p_{\sigma(m)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(m)}}$ and p divides only $p_{\sigma(1)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(1)}}, p_{\sigma(2)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(2)}} \dots$ and $p_{\sigma(d)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(d)}}$, then $p_{\sigma(d+1)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(d+1)}} \dots p_{\sigma(m)}^{\alpha_{\sigma(m)}}$ divides $x - 1$.

We start our study by the following theorem:

Theorem 2.1: Let n be an integer whose decomposition in prime factors is $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with $p_i \neq p$ for all i and p divides only $p_1 - 1$, then $G_p(n)$ is a cyclic subgroup of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ of order p .

Proof :

Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , we have $p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ divides $x - 1$, then x is a solution of one of the following systems :

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1^{\alpha_1} K' \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} x - 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = K' \end{cases}$$

Clearly, 1 is the unique solution of the second system. Now, we will show that the first system have exactly $p - 1$ solutions, which follows immediately from the two following lemmas.

Lemma 2.3: The systems

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1^{\alpha_1} K' \end{cases} \quad (*)$$

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1 K' \end{cases} \quad (**)$$

have the same number of solutions respectively modulo n and $n/p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$.

Proof :

It is clear that any solution of $(*)$ is a solution of $(**)$. Reciprocally let x be a solution of $(**)$, then $x^p \equiv 1 [p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}]$

that is to say $x^p = 1 + p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_1$ and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} x^{p p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} &= (1 + p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_1)^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} - 1} C_{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}}^i (p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_1)^i + \\ &\quad (p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_1)^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} \end{aligned}$$

It is easily verified that all $C_{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}}^i$ are divisible by $p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}$ and $p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} \geq \alpha_1$, then $x^{p p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} \equiv 1 [n]$. From the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} x^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} &= (1 + p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K)^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} - 1} C_{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}}^i (p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K)^i + \\ &\quad (p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K)^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} \end{aligned}$$

and as the $C_{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}}^i$ are divisible by p_1 and K is not divisible by p_1 , then $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} - 1$ is divisible by all the p_i except p_1 and consequently $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}}$ is a solution of (\star) .

Let x and y be two solutions of $(\star\star)$ such as $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} = y^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} [n]$ and thus $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} = y^{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}} [p_1]$, hence $x \equiv y [p_1]$, on the other hand it is clear that $x \equiv y [p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}]$ and consequently $x \equiv y [p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}]$. We therefore conclude that the number of solutions of (\star) is greater than or equal to that of $(\star\star)$. Thus the systems (\star) and $(\star\star)$ have the same number of solutions modulo n and $n/p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}$ respectively. ■

Lemma 2.4: The following system

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1 K' \end{cases} \quad (\star\star)$$

has $p - 1$ solutions modulo $n/p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}$.

Proof:

We know that $\mathbb{Z}/p_1\mathbb{Z}$ is the field of decomposition of the polynomial $X^{p_1} - X$, and more precisely we have :

$$X^{p_1} - X = \prod_{i=0}^{p_1-1} (X - i)$$

and therefore

$$X^{p_1-1} - 1 = \prod_{i=1}^{p_1-1} (X - i)$$

and as p divides $p_1 - 1$ then the polynomial $X^p - 1$ divides $X^{p_1-1} - 1$ and therefore the polynomial $X^p - 1$ is also a product of factors of degree 1, that is to say

$$X^p - 1 = \prod_{i=1}^p (X - \gamma_i)$$

and as 1 is a root of $X^p - 1$ then we take $\gamma_1 = 1$ and finally we obtain

$$1 + X + X^2 + \dots + X^{p-1} = \prod_{i=2}^p (X - \gamma_i)$$

and consequently the system $(\star\star)$ is equivalent to the following systems:

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_2 \\ x - \gamma_2 = p_1 K'_2 \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_3 \\ x - \gamma_3 = p_1 K'_3 \end{cases} \\ \dots \quad \begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_p \\ x - \gamma_p = p_1 K'_p \end{cases}$$

It is clear that each of these systems has only one solution modulo $p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$. Also the solutions of these systems are 2 by 2 distinct. Indeed if we denote x_i the solution of the following system

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K_i \\ x - \gamma_i = p_1 K'_i \end{cases}$$

then $x_i \equiv \gamma_i [p_1]$. Since the γ_i are distinct modulo p_1 , then the x_i are also distinct. We conclude that $(\star\star)$ have $p - 1$ solutions modulo $n/p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}$. ■

Remark :

The proof of the previous theorem gives an algorithm for calculating the solutions of (\star) , and this is done in two steps :

Step 1

We resolve $(\star\star)$, the most difficult point in this step is to determinate the γ_i . We must give the factorization of the polynomial $1 + X + X^2 + \dots + X^{p-1}$ in the field $\mathbb{Z}/p_1\mathbb{Z}[X]$ and for this we can use Berlekamp's algorithm [8] or Cantor-Zassenhaus algorithm [9]. Then we decompose $(\star\star)$ in small systems that are resolved easily with Euclidian's algorithm.

Step 2

To find the solutions of (\star) , it is sufficient to see that they are also solutions of $(\star\star)$ set to the power $p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1}$ modulo n .

Note also that the set of solutions of (\star) forms with 1 a cyclic group of order p , then any solution of (\star) generates this group. Thus in practice it is sufficient to determine a solution of (\star) to find the others.

A sample calculation :

We want to determine the elements of order 7 modulo n with $n = 10609215 = 29^4 * 5 * 3$. The first step consists to give the factorization of $1 + X + X^2 + \dots + X^6$ in the field $\mathbb{Z}/29\mathbb{Z}[X]$, by using Berlekamp's algorithm, we obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} &1 + X + X^2 + \dots + X^6 \\ &= (X + 4)(X + 5)(X + 6)(X + 9)(X + 13)(X + 22). \end{aligned}$$

Let's consider the following system

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = 15K \\ x + 4 = 29K' \end{cases}$$

which gives $29K' - 15K = 5$, and by the euclidian algorithm we obtain $K' = -5$ and $K = -10$.

Therefore $x = -149 = 286$ modulo $435 = 29 * 5 * 3$. Thereby $286^{29^3} \bmod n = 1006441$ is an element of order 7 modulo n and consequently the elements of $\mathbf{G}_7(n)$ are

$$\mathbf{G}_7(n) = \{1006441, 1006441^2, \dots, 1006441^7\}$$

that is to say

$$\mathbf{G}_7(n) = \{1006441, 8684356, 6860611, 4797001, 5450251, 9979951, 1\}$$

Now, we give an algorithm in *MAPLE* which allows us for any fixed integer n and a prime odd number p , as described in the last theorem, to give a generator of the cyclic group $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$.

```
Gene_p := proc(n, p) local LB, LD, P, gen, i, LFact;
LD := []; LB := [];
LFact := ifactors(n)[2];
for i from 1 to nops(LFact) do
if (LFact[i][1] - 1 mod p = 0) then
LD := [op(LD), LFact[i]];
end;
end;
P := convert(Berlekamp(x^p - 1, x) mod LD[1][1], list);
if (P[1] - x + 1 mod LD[1][1] <> 0) then
LB := Bezout(LD[1][1], n/(LD[1][1]^LD[1][2]), P[1] - x + 1);
gen := ((LD[1][1] * LB[1] - (P[1] - x) mod n) &^
(LD[1][1]^(LD[1][2] - 1))) mod n;
else
LB := Bezout(LD[1][1], n/(LD[1][1]^LD[1][2]), P[2] - x + 1);
gen := (LD[1][1] * LB[1] - (P[2] - x) mod n) &^
(LD[1][1]^(LD[1][2] - 1))) mod n;
end;
eval(gen);
end;
```

Algorithm 2.1

Remark :

The Berlekamp's procedure used in this algorithm is predefined in *MAPLE*.

In the remainder of this paragraph, considering an integer n whose decomposition in prime factors is $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ and p a prime odd number such that $p_i \neq p$ for all i . For a fixed permutation we can write $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} p_{d+1}^{\alpha_{d+1}} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with p divides $p_i - 1$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$. We have seen that if x is a p -th root of unity modulo n , then $p_{d+1}^{\alpha_{d+1}} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ divides $x - 1$. Thus $p_{d+1}^{\alpha_{d+1}} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ don't have a significant role in our study, for the rest we set $p_{d+1}^{\alpha_{d+1}} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} = A$.

Definition 2.2: Let x a p -th root of unity modulo n , we say that x is initial if all the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ divides $x - 1$ except for only one p_i . We say that this p -th root is associated to p_i , and we write :

$$x - 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK.$$

with K is an integer not divisible par p_i .

We denote by $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$ the set formed by the unity and the initial p -th roots of unity associated to p_i , and we have the following theorem :

Theorem 2.2: $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$ is a cyclic subgroup of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ with cardinality p .

Proof :

The initial p -th roots of unity associated to p_i are the solutions of the system :

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK & (*) \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_i^{\alpha_i} K' \end{cases}$$

We saw in the foregoing that this system have $p - 1$ solutions modulo n and then $\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)) = p$. Let's prove now that $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$ is a subgroup. Let x and y be two solutions of $(*)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x - 1 &= p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK \text{ and} \\ y - 1 &= p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK' \end{aligned}$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} x.y &= 1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A(K \\ &+ K' + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AKK') \end{aligned}$$

Note that $x.y$ is a p -th root of unity and therefore at this stage we have two case. If p_i divides $(K + K' + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AKK')$, then $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides $x.y - 1$ and we obtain $x.y = 1$. If p_i does not divide $(K + K' + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AKK')$, then $x.y$ is an initial to p -th root of unity associated to p_i . It is clear that if x is a p -th root of unity, then its inverse $x^{-1} = x^{p-1}$ is an element of $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$. Whereof $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$ is a cyclic subgroup of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ because its cardinality is a prime number p . ■

Proposition 2.3: Let x and y be two initial p -th roots of unity associated to p_i and p_j with $i \neq j$, then $x.y$ is a p -th root of unity satisfying

$$x.y - 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_j^{\alpha_j} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK$$

with K is an integer which is not divisible by p_i and p_j .

Proof :

We have

$$\begin{aligned} x - 1 &= p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_1 \text{ and} \\ y - 1 &= p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_j^{\alpha_j} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_2 \end{aligned}$$

and therefore

$$x.y = 1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_j^{\alpha_j} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A(p_i^{\alpha_i} K_1 + p_i^{\alpha_i} K_2)$$

and as p_i does not divide K_1 also p_j does not divide K_2 , then $(p_i^{\alpha_j} K_1 + p_i^{\alpha_i} K_2)$ is not divisible by both p_i and p_j . ■

Definition 2.3: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , we say that it is final if all the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ does not divide $x - 1$, that is to say $x - 1 = AK$, with K an integer not divisible by any $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$.

Remark :

The existence of final p -th roots of unity modulo n is ensured by the preceding proposition, in fact if for all $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ we take x_i an initial p -th root of unity associated to p_i , then $\prod_{i=1}^d x_i$ is a final p -th root of unity modulo n .

Definition 2.4: Let x and y be two p -th roots of unity modulo n , we say that y is a final conjugate of x if $x.y - 1$ is not divisible by any of the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, that is to say $x.y$ is a final p -th root of unity modulo n .

Proposition 2.4: Any p -th root of unity modulo n have a final conjugate.

Proof :

If $x = 1$ or x is a final p -th root of unity modulo n , then we have the result. When $d = 1$, then a final p -th root of unity modulo n is also an initial p -th root of unity associated to p_1 and thus all the p -th roots of unity distinct from 1 are final. Now, we suppose that $d \geq 2$ and $x - 1$ is divisible by a nonempty subset of p_i of cardinality $t < d$ and we can assume that, for a fixed permutation, this p_i are p_1, p_2, \dots are p_t and thus

$$x - 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} AK$$

with K is an integer which is not divisible by any of the $p_i, i \in \{t+1, \dots, d\}$. For all $i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$ let x_i be an initial p -th root of unity associated to p_i and therefore

$$x_i = 1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$$

with K_i not divisible by p_i , and thus

$$\prod_{i=1}^t x_i = \prod_{i=1}^t (1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)$$

$$= 1 + p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A \sum_{i=1}^t p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} K_i + K'n$$

but $\sum_{i=1}^t p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} K_i$ is not divisible by any of the

$p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$ therefore $y = \prod_{i=1}^t x_i$ is a p -th root of unity

satisfies $y = 1 + p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AM$ with M an integer which is not divisible by $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$. So

$$x.y = 1 + A(p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AM + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} AK)$$

It is clear that $(p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AM + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} AK)$ is not divisible by any of the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, and hence the result. ■

Theorem 2.3: Let x be a final p -th root of unity modulo n , then it exists d integers K_1, K_2, \dots, K_d such as:

$$x = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$$

and

$$(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p = 1 [n] \quad \forall 1 \leq i \leq d.$$

Proof :

Since $p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d}$ and $p_d^{\alpha_d}$ are coprime then it exists two integers \tilde{K}'_d and \tilde{K}_d such as

$$1 = p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}_d \quad (*)$$

and therefore

$$x - 1 = p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_d + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_d$$

with $K'_d = ((x - 1)/A)\tilde{K}'_d$ and $K_d = ((x - 1)/A)\tilde{K}_d$. We have :

$$\begin{aligned} (x - p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_d)^p &= (x - (x - 1)p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d)^p \\ &= (a(1 - p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d) + p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d)^p \\ &= (xp_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}_d + p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d)^p \\ &= (p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}_d)^p + (p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d)^p \quad [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d}] \\ &= 1 [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d}] \quad \text{from } (*) \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} x - (x - 1)p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d &= 1 + (x - 1)(1 - p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d) \\ &= 1 [A] \end{aligned}$$

Thus $(x - (x - 1)p_d^{\alpha_d} \tilde{K}'_d)^p = 1[n]$ and consequently $(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_d)^p = 1[n]$.

Suppose that it exists some integers K_t, K_2, \dots, K_d and K'_t such as :

$$x = 1 + \sum_{i=t}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i + p_t^{\alpha_t} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t$$

and

$$(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p = 1 [n] \quad \forall t \leq i \leq d$$

Let \tilde{K}'_{t-1} and \tilde{K}_{t-1} be two integers such as

$$1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}_{t-1} + p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}'_{t-1} \quad (**)$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t &= p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1} + \\ & p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1}. \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & (p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1 - p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p \\ &= ((p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1)(1 - p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}'_{t-1}) + p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p \\ &= ((p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1)p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}_{t-1} + p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p \\ &= (p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1)^p (p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}_{t-1})^p + (p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}}] \end{aligned}$$

however

$$\begin{aligned} & (p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1)^p \\ &= (x - \sum_{i=t}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p \\ &= x^p [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} A] \\ &= 1 [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} A] \end{aligned}$$

and consequently

$$\begin{aligned} & (p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1 - p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p \\ &= (p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}_{t-1})^p + (p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}}] \\ &= 1 [p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}}] \text{ from } (***) \end{aligned}$$

also it is clear that

$$(p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1 - p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p = 1 [p_d^{\alpha_d} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} A]$$

and so

$$(p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t + 1 - p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1})^p = 1 [n]$$

That means

$$(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_t \tilde{K}_{t-1})^p = 1 [n].$$

We set $K_{t-1} = K'_t \tilde{K}_{t-1}$ and $K'_{t-1} = K'_t \tilde{K}'_{t-1}$, we obtain so

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 1 + \sum_{i=t}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_{t-1} + p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_{t-1} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=t-1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i + p_{t-1}^{\alpha_{t-1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_{t-1} \end{aligned}$$

with

$$(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p = 1 [n] \quad \forall t-1 \leq i \leq d$$

Thus by induction, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'_1 \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i \quad [n] \end{aligned}$$

with $(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p = 1 [n], \forall 1 \leq i \leq d. \blacksquare$

Corollary 2.2: Any final p -th root of unity modulo n is a product of d initial p -th roots associated respectively to p_1, p_2, \dots and p_d .

Proof:

From the precedent theorem, it exists some integers K_1, K_2, \dots, K_d such as:

$$x = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$$

and

$$(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p = 1 [n] \quad \forall 1 \leq i \leq d$$

If we set $x_i = 1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$, then x_i is a p -th root of unity modulo n also from the construction of K_i in the preceding proof, K_i is not divisible by p_i . Thus x_i is an initial p -th root associated to p_i . On the other hand we have

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=1}^d x_i &= \prod_{i=1}^d (1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i [n] = x. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.3: Every p -th root of unity modulo n is a product of initial p -th roots.

Proof:

Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , if this root is final, then the result is immediate, otherwise there is x_1, x_2, \dots and

x_t such as $x = \prod_{i=1}^t x_i$ is final p -th root of unity modulo n and from the precedent corollary there exists y_1, y_2, \dots and y_d initial p -th roots of unity modulo n associated respectively

to p_1, p_2, \dots and p_d such as $x = \prod_{i=1}^t x_i = \prod_{i=1}^d y_i$ and thus

$x = \prod_{i=1}^t x_i^{-1} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^d y_i$ and as the set of initial p -th roots of unity modulo n associated to p_i form with 1 a group, then x can be written like following $x = \prod_{i=1}^d z_i$ with z_i is either 1 or an initial p -th root associated to $p_i. \blacksquare$

Corollary 2.4: $G_p(n)$ is generated by the initial p -th roots of unity modulo n .

Remark:

As for each p_i the set of initial p -th roots of unity modulo n associated to p_i form with 1 a cyclic group then

$$G_p(n) = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d \rangle$$

with x_i an initial p -th root of unity modulo n associated to p_i .

Theorem 2.4: The map

$$\varphi : \mathbf{G}_p^{p_1}(n) \times \mathbf{G}_p^{p_2}(n) \dots \times \mathbf{G}_p^{p_d}(n) \longrightarrow \mathbf{G}_p(n)$$

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) \longmapsto x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot \dots \cdot x_d$$

is an isomorphism of groups.

Proof :

We have shown that φ is a surjective morphism of groups, remains to prove that it is injective.

We have $\varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) = 1 \iff x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot \dots \cdot x_d = 1$, assume that there exists an integer i such that $x_i \neq 1$, then we can easily verify that $x_1 \cdot x_2 \cdot \dots \cdot x_d - 1$ is also not divisible by p_i but this is absurd, thus $x_i = 1$ for all i and hence φ is injective. ■

From the previous theorem it is clear that $Card(\mathbf{G}_p(n)) = p^d$, where d is a number of distinct prime factors q of n such that p divides $q - 1$, that is to say $d = \alpha_p(n)$ and we obtain the following result :

Corollary 2.5:

$$Card(\mathbf{G}_p(n)) = p^{\alpha_p(n)}.$$

Remark :

From the previous theorem we have

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \left\{ \prod_{(i_1, i_2, \dots, i_d) \in I^d} x_1^{i_1} x_2^{i_2} \dots x_d^{i_d} \text{ , with } I = \{1, 2, \dots, p\} \right\}$$

with x_i is a generator of the cyclic group $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$.

We give now an algorithm written in Maple that allows us from an integer n and an odd prime p , as described in this foregoing, to give a generating set of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$.

```
Gene_p := proc(n,p) local LB, LD, i, LFact, GEN, P;
LD := [ ]; LB := [ ]; GEN := [ ];
LFact := ifactors(n)[2];
for i from 1 to nops(LFact) do
if (LFact[i][1] - 1 mod p = 0) then
LD := [op(LD), LFact[i]];
end :
end :
for i from 1 to nops(LD) do
P := convert(Berlekamp(x^p - 1, x) mod LD[i][1], list);
if (P[1] - x + 1 mod LD[i][1] <> 0) then
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[1] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), ((LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[1] - x) mod n) &^ (LD[i][1]^(LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n)];
else
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[2] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), (LD[i][1]*LB[1] - (P[2] - x) mod n) &^ (LD[i][1]^(LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n];
end :
end :
if (GEN = [ ]) then
```

$GEN := [1];$

$end :$

$eval(GEN);$

$end :$

Algorithm 2.2

A sample application :

Let $n = 53 * 79 * 131 * 17 * 19$ and $p = 13$, to find a generating set of the group formed by the p -th roots of unity modulo n , it suffices to use the previous algorithm with the command line $Gene_p(n, 13)$. The displayed result is [50140906, 174921943, 71677254], which represents the list of generators of this group.

Remark :

In the case when this algorithm return [1], then this means that $G_p(n) = \{1\}$.

Case 2 : $\alpha = 1$

Let n be an integer whose decomposition into prime factors is $n = p p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with $p_i \neq p$ for all i and let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , the above results show that if p does not divide $p_i - 1$ then $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides $x - 1$, on the other hand we have $x^p = 1[n]$ implies that p divides $(x - 1)(1 + x + \dots + x^{p-1})$ and from the lemma 2.1 we obtain p divides $x - 1$ and $1 + x + \dots + x^{p-1}$.

Also provided p divides $\lambda(n)$ implies that there exists at least one integer i such that p divides $p_i - 1$. For a fixed permutation we can write $n = p p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with p divides $p_i - 1$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and does not divide $p_i - 1$ for every $i \in \{d + 1, \dots, m\}$. Assume for the following $p_{d+1}^{\alpha_{d+1}} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} = A$. We define in the same manner the initial p -th roots of unity modulo n by replacing A with pA . The initial p -th roots of unity modulo n associated to $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ are the solutions of the system :

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} pAK \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_i^{\alpha_i} K' \end{cases}$$

We show in the same manner that this system has exactly $p - 1$ roots modulo n . Thus for all $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ there are $p - 1$ initial p -th roots associated to p_i . We also show that the initial p -th roots of unity modulo n associated to p_i form with 1 a cyclic subgroup of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ of cardinality p and it is denoted as $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$.

We define in the same way a final p -th root of unity and its conjugate by replacing A by pA and we obtain the following theorem :

Theorem 2.5: Let x be a final p -th root of unity modulo n , then there exists integers K_1, K_2, \dots, K_d such that :

$$x = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} pAK_i$$

and

$$(1 + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} pAK_i)^p = 1 \quad \forall 1 \leq i \leq d.$$

Indeed to prove this result we can just proceed as above and replacing A by pA .

We deduce that any final p -th root of unity modulo n is the product of d initial p -th roots associated respectively to p_1, p_2, \dots and p_d . Hence every p -th root of unity is the product of initial p -th roots, and we can show that $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is generated by the initial p -th roots of unity and more precisely if we denote x_i an initial p -th root of unity associated to p_i , then

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d \rangle.$$

Also we have the following results :

Theorem 2.6: The map

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi : \mathbf{G}_p^{p_1}(n) \times \mathbf{G}_p^{p_2}(n) \dots \times \mathbf{G}_p^{p_d}(n) &\longrightarrow \mathbf{G}_p(n) \\ (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) &\longmapsto x_1 x_2 \dots x_d \end{aligned}$$

is an isomorphism of groups.

Corollary 2.6:

$$\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p(n)) = p^{\alpha_p(n)}.$$

Remark :

From the previous theorem we can easily show that

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \left\{ \prod_{(i_1, i_2, \dots, i_d) \in I^d} x_1^{i_1} x_2^{i_2} \dots x_d^{i_d}, \text{ with } I = \{1, 2, \dots, p\} \right\}$$

with x_i is a generator of the cyclic group $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$.

Finally, note that *Algorithm 2.2* remains valid in this case.

Case 3 : $\alpha \geq 2$

Let n be an integer whose decomposition into prime factors is $n = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with $p_i \neq p$ for all i and $\alpha \geq 2$. The fact that $\alpha \geq 2$ ensures that $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is not reduced to $\{1\}$.

Suppose that for every i , p does not divide $p_i - 1$ and let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , then $p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ divides $x - 1$ and by *Proposition 2.2* it follows that $p^{\alpha-1}$ divides $x - 1$. So x is a solution of the system

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = K' \end{cases}$$

But this system has p solutions modulo n which are $1, 1 + n/p, 1 + 2n/p, \dots$ and $1 + (p-1)n/p$. Then we obtain the following result:

Proposition 2.5: Let $n = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with $\alpha \geq 2$ and p does not divide $p_i - 1$ for all i , then

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \{1 + kn/p; \quad 0 \leq k \leq p-1\}$$

Remark:

It is clear that $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is a cyclic group of order p .

We will now exclude this case from our study, that is, there exists at least i such that p divides $p_i - 1$. For a fixed permutation we can write $n = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m}$ with p divides $p_i - 1$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and does not divide $p_i - 1$ for all $i \in \{d+1, \dots, m\}$ and assume for the rest of this paper $p_{d+1}^{\alpha_{d+1}} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} = A$.

Definition 2.5: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , x is said of class zero if $x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK$ with K an integer.

It is clear that there are p p -th roots of unity of class zero which are $\{1 + kn/p; \quad 0 \leq k \leq p-1\}$ and one can easily verify that they form a cyclic group of order p denoted $\mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$.

Definition 2.6: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , it is said initial root if every $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ divides $x - 1$ except for only one p_i . We said that this root is associated to p_i . And we write :

$$x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK.$$

with K an integer that is not divided by p_i .

Theorem 2.7: There exists $p^2 - p$ initial p -th roots of unity associated to p_i for all $1 \leq i \leq d$.

Proof :

We may assume $i = 1$, the initial p -th roots associated to p_1 are the solutions of the system :

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1^{\alpha_1} K' \end{cases} \quad (\star)$$

and we conclude with the following lemmas. ■

Lemma 2.5: The following systems have the same number of solutions respectively modulo n and $n/p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$.

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1^{\alpha_1} K' \end{cases} \quad (\star)$$

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1 K' \end{cases} \quad (\star\star)$$

Proof :

It is clear that any solution of (\star) is a solution of $(\star\star)$. Reciprocally let x be a solution of $(\star\star)$, then $x^p \equiv 1 [p^\alpha p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A]$ that is to say $x^p = 1 + p^\alpha p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_1$ and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} x^{pp_1^{\alpha_1-1}} &= (1 + p^\alpha p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_1)^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}-1} \mathbf{C}_{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}}^i (p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_1)^i \\ &\quad + (p^\alpha p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_1)^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} \end{aligned}$$

It is easily verified that all $C_{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}}^i$ are divisible by $p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$ and $p_1^{\alpha_1-1} \geq \alpha_1$, then $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} \equiv 1 [n]$. On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} x^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} &= (1 + p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK)^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}-1} C_{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}}^i (p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK)^i \\ &\quad + (p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK)^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} \end{aligned}$$

And as $C_{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}}^i$ are divisible by p_1 and K is not divisible by p_1 , then $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} - 1$ is divisible by all p_i except p_1 . Consequently $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}}$ is a solution of (\star) .

Let x and y be two solutions of $(\star\star)$ such that $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} = y^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} [n]$ thus $x^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} = y^{p_1^{\alpha_1-1}} [p_1]$. Hence $x \equiv y [p_1]$, on the other hand it is clear that $x \equiv y [p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A]$ therefore $x \equiv y [p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A]$. We conclude then that the systems (\star) and $(\star\star)$ have the same number of solutions respectively modulo n and $n/p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$. ■

Lemma 2.6: The following system have $p^2 - p$ solutions modulo $n/p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$.

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_m^{\alpha_m} K \\ 1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{p-1} = p_1 K' \end{cases} \quad (\star\star)$$

Proof :

We know that

$$X^p - 1 = \prod_{i=1}^p (X - \gamma_i)$$

and as 1 is a root of $X^p - 1$ then we take $\gamma_1 = 1$. Finally, we obtain

$$1 + X + X^2 + \dots + X^{p-1} = \prod_{i=2}^p (X - \gamma_i)$$

and consequently $(\star\star)$ is equivalent to the following systems :

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_2 \\ x - \gamma_2 = p_1 K'_2 \\ \vdots \\ x - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_p \\ x - \gamma_p = p_1 K'_p \end{cases}$$

It is clear that for each one of these systems have p solutions modulo $n/p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$. Since, the solutions of these systems are distinct, we conclude that $(\star\star)$ have $p(p-1)$ solutions modulo $n/p_1^{\alpha_1-1}$. ■

Proposition 2.6: The set formed by the initial p -th roots of unity modulo n associated to p_i and by the elements of $G_p^0(n)$ is a subgroup of $G_p(n)$ denoted $G_p^{p_i}(n)$ and we have $Card(G_p^{p_i}(n)) = p^2$.

Proof :

Let x and y be two elements of $G_p^{p_i}(n)$, there are three cases

to distinguish :

- If x and y are in $G_p^0(n)$, then in this case xy belongs $G_p^0(n)$ since the latter is a group and hence xy is in $G_p^{p_i}(n)$.
- If x and y are respectively in $G_p^{p_i}(n) \setminus G_p^0(n)$ and $G_p^0(n)$,

then we have $x - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK$ and $y - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'$ with K an integer not divisible by p_i thus

$$xy = 1 + p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A(K + p_i^{\alpha_i} K')$$

The term $K + p_i^{\alpha_i} K'$ is not divided by p_i and therefore xy is a p -th root of unity associated to p_i . Hence xy is in $G_p^{p_i}(n)$.

- If x and y are in $G_p^{p_i}(n) \setminus G_p^0(n)$, then :

$x - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK$ and $y - 1 = p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'$ with K and K' are two integers not divided by p_i therefore

$$\begin{aligned} xy &= 1 + p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A(K + K') \\ &\quad + p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AKK' \end{aligned}$$

If the term $K + K' + p^{\alpha_1-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AKK'$ is divided by p_i then xy belongs to $G_p^0(n) \subset G_p^{p_i}(n)$, otherwise xy is a p -th root associated to p_i and consequently xy is in $G_p^{p_i}(n)$.

Thus $G_p^{p_i}(n)$ is stable for the product and as the inverse of the element x is x^{p-1} , then $G_p^{p_i}(n)$ is stable by the inverse operation which proves that $G_p^{p_i}(n)$ is a subgroup of $G_p(n)$. Finally, we can see that $G_p^0(n)$ does not contain an initial p -th root associated to p_i which allows us to conclude that $Card(G_p^{p_i}(n)) = (p^2 - p) + p = p^2$. ■

Definition 2.7: Let x be a p -th root, we said that x is of the first class if p^α divides $x - 1$, otherwise it said to be of the second class.

Proposition 2.7: There are $p - 1$ initial p -th roots of unity associated to p_i which are of the first class.

Proof :

The initial p -th roots associated to p_i which are of first class are solutions of the system :

$$\begin{cases} x - 1 = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK \\ x + 1 = p_i^{\alpha_i} K' \end{cases}$$

And from the previous we know that this system has $p - 1$ solutions modulo n . ■

Let denote by $G_p^+(n)$ the set formed by 1 and the initial p -th roots of unity associated to p_i that are of the first class and we can easily verify that $G_p^+(n)$ is a cyclic subgroup of $G_p(n)$ of cardinality p and we have the following result :

Proposition 2.8: The map

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi : G_p^+(n) \times G_p^0(n) &\longrightarrow G_p^{p_i}(n) \\ (x, y) &\longmapsto x.y \end{aligned}$$

is an isomorphism of groups.

Proof :

It is clear that φ is surjective morphism of groups. For the injectivity, let us consider two elements x and y of $\mathbf{G}_p^{+1}(n)$ and $\mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$ respectively such that $x.y = 1$, we have :

$$x - 1 = p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK \text{ and } y - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK', \text{ therefore}$$

$$xy = 1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A(K + p_i^{\alpha_i} K').$$

As $x.y = 1$, then the term $K + p_i^{\alpha_i} K'$ is divided by $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ therefore $p_i^{\alpha_i}$ divides K , hence $x = y = 1$. ■

Definition 2.8: Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , we said x is final if all the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ does not divide $x - 1$, which means $x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} AK$, with K an integer not divisible by $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$.

Proposition 2.9: Any final p -th root of unity modulo n can be written in a single manner as product of a final p -th root of the first class by a class zero's p -th root.

Proof :

Let x be a final p -th root of unity modulo n and let's consider an integer y of the form $y = 1 + p^\alpha AK$ and z a class zero's p -th root. We have :

$$\begin{aligned} x = yz &\iff x = (1 + p^\alpha AK)(1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK') \\ &\iff x - 1 = p^\alpha AK + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK' \\ &\iff \frac{x - 1}{p^{\alpha-1} A} = pK + p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} K' \end{aligned}$$

This equation has solutions K and K' , also $(1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK')^p = 1$, therefore $(1 + p^\alpha AK)^p = 1$ and as $x - 1$ is divisible by none of the p_i which implies that K is divisible by none of the p_i , this proves that $(1 + p^\alpha AK)$ is a final p -th root of the first class. Also it is clear that if we take K and K' as other solutions, then $1 + p^\alpha AK$ and $1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK'$ are the same modulo n . ■

Remark :

If for all $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ we take x_i an initial p -th root of the first class associated to p_i , then $\prod_{i=1}^d x_i$ is a final root of the first class. The following theorem shows that any final root of the first class is a product of this form.

Theorem 2.8: Any final p -th root of the first class is product of d initial p -th roots of the first class associated respectively to p_1, p_2, \dots and p_d .

Proof :

Let x be a final p -th root of the first class, we know that there

exist K_1, K_2, \dots and K_d such that

$$x = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^d p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$$

and

$$(1 + p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)^p = 1 [n] \quad \forall 1 \leq i \leq d.$$

If we set $x_i = 1 + p^\alpha p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$, then x_i is an initial p -th root of the first class associated to p_i and we can easily verify that $x = \prod_{i=1}^d x_i$. ■

Definition 2.9: Let x and y be two p -th roots of unity modulo n , we say y is a final conjugate root of x if $x.y - 1$ is divisible by none of the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, that means $x.y$ is a final p -th root modulo n .

Proposition 2.10: Any p -th root of unity modulo n have a final conjugate.

Proof :

Let x be a p -th root of unity modulo n , if $x \in \mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$ or x is a final p -th root then we have the expected result. When $d = 1$, a final p -th root is an initial p -th root associated to p_1 and therefore any root that not belongs to $\mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$ are finals. Assume that $d \geq 2$ and $x - 1$ is divisible by a nonempty subfamily of p_i of cardinality $t < d$ and for a permutation, we can assume them p_1, p_2, \dots and p_t . Thus

$$x - 1 = p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} AK$$

with K an integer not divisible by $p_i, i \in \{t+1, \dots, d\}$. For all $i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$, let x_i be an initial p -th associated to p_i therefore

$$x_i = 1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i$$

with K_i not divided by p_i , whereof

$$\prod_{i=1}^t x_i = \prod_{i=1}^t (1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AK_i)$$

$$= 1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} A \sum_{i=1}^t p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} K_i + K' n$$

but $\sum_{i=1}^t p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} K_i$ is divisible by none of the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, t\}$. Consequently $y = \prod_{i=1}^t x_i$ is a root which verify

$$y = 1 + p^{\alpha-1} p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AM \text{ with } M \text{ an integer that not divided by } p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, t\}. \text{ Thereby}$$

$$x.y = 1 + p^{\alpha-1} A(p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AM + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} AK)$$

It is clear that $(p_{t+1}^{\alpha_{t+1}} \dots p_d^{\alpha_d} AM + p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t} AK)$ is divisible by none of the $p_i, i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, hence the result. ■

Corollary 2.7: Every p -th root of unity is a product of a first class initial p -th roots by a class zero's p -th root.

Proof :

Let x be a p -th root modulo n , if x is final then we can write it as a product of a final p -th root of unity of the first class by a class zero's p -th root and from the previous results this final p -th root of the first class is product of d initial p -th roots of the first class associated respectively to p_1, p_2, \dots and p_d , hence the result. Now let us assume that x is not a final p -th root so there exists x_1, x_2, \dots and x_t initial p -th roots such that $x_1 x_2 \dots x_t$ is a final conjugate of x , then $x x_1 x_2 \dots x_t$ is a final p -th root, and we have :

$$x x_1 x_2 \dots x_t = y_1 y_2 \dots y_d y_0$$

with y_i is an initial p -th root of the first class associated to p_i and y_0 is a class zero's p -th root.

From Proposition 2.8 any initial p -th root associated to p_i can be written uniquely as a product of an initial first class p -th root associated to p_i by class zero's p -th root. Thereby $x_i = x_i^+ z_i$, with $x_i^+ \in \mathbf{G}_p^{p_1}(n)$ and $z_i \in \mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$. So

$$x = y_1 y_2 \dots y_d (x_1^+ x_2^+ \dots x_t^+)^{-1} (z_1 z_2 \dots z_t)^{-1} y_0$$

and as $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_1}(n)$ and $\mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$ are groups, then we obtain the result. ■

Remark :

The previous result shows that $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$ is generated by the initial p -th roots of the first class and the class zero's p -th roots and as $\mathbf{G}_p^0(n)$ and $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_1}(n)$ are cyclic groups, then

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \langle x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d, x_0 \rangle$$

with x_i is an initial p -th root of the first class associated to p_i and x_0 is a p -th root of the class zero distinct from 1. More generally, we have the following result :

Theorem 2.9: The map

$$\varphi : \mathbf{G}_p^{p_1}(n) \times \mathbf{G}_p^{p_2}(n) \dots \times \mathbf{G}_p^{p_m}(n) \times \mathbf{G}_p^0(n) \longrightarrow \mathbf{G}_p(n)$$

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m, y) \longmapsto x_1 x_2 \dots x_m y$$

is an isomorphism of groups.

Proof :

It is clear that φ is a surjective morphism of groups and we show that it is injective as in the analogous previous results. ■

Corollary 2.8:

$$\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p(n)) = p^{\alpha_p(n)+1}.$$

Remark :

From the previous theorem we have

$$\mathbf{G}_p(n) = \left\{ \prod_{(i_1, i_2, \dots, i_d, i) \in I^{d+1}} x_1^{i_1} x_2^{i_2} \dots x_d^{i_d} x_0^i \right\}$$

with $I = \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$, x_i is one generator of the cyclic group $\mathbf{G}_p^{p_i}(n)$ for $i \neq 0$ and x_0 is a p -th root of the first class different from 1.

We now give an algorithm in *MAPLE* that allows us to find a generating set of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$. For the computing of x_0 it suffices to take $x_0 = 1 + n/p$ and for the others x_i , we proceed as above.

```
Gene_p := proc(n,p) local LB, LD, i, LFact, GEN, P;
LD := []; LB := []; GEN := [];
GEN := [op(GEN), 1 + n/p];
LFact := ifactors(n)[2];
for i from 1 to nops(LFact) do
if (LFact[i][1] - 1 mod p = 0) then
LD := [op(LD), LFact[i]];
end;
end;
for i from 1 to nops(LD) do
P := convert(Berlekamp(x^p - 1, x) mod LD[i][1], list);
if (P[1] - x + 1 mod LD[i][1] <> 0) then
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[1] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), ((LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[1] - x) mod n) &^ (LD[i][1]^LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n];
else
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[2] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), (LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[2] - x) mod n) &^ (LD[i][1]^LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n];
end;
end;
if (GEN = []) then
GEN := [1];
end;
eval(GEN);
end;
```

Algorithm 2.3

III. CONCLUSION

For the cardinality of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$, we can summarize it in the following theorem :

Theorem 3.1: Let $n \geq 3$ be an integer and p be a prime odd number which does not divide n , then :

- $\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p(n)) = p^{\alpha_p(n)}$
- $\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p(pn)) = p^{\alpha_p(n)}$
- $\text{Card}(\mathbf{G}_p(p^\alpha n)) = p^{\alpha_p(n)+1}$ with $\alpha \geq 2$

We will now give an algorithm which help us to find, from a fixed integer n , a generating set of $\mathbf{G}_p(n)$.

```
Gene_p := proc(n,p) local LB, LD, i, LFact, GEN, P;
LD := []; LB := []; GEN := [];
if (n mod p^2 = 0) then
GEN := [op(GEN), 1 + n/p];
LFact := ifactors(n)[2];
for i from 1 to nops(LFact) do
if (LFact[i][1] - 1 mod p = 0) then
```

```

LD := [op(LD), LFact[i]];
end :
end :
for i from 1 to nops(LD) do
P := convert(Berlekamp(x^p - 1, x) mod LD[i][1], list);
if (P[1] - x + 1 mod LD[i][1] <> 0) then
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[1] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), ((LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[1] - x) mod n) &^(LD[i][1]^(LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n)];
else
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[2] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), (LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[2] - x) mod n) &^(LD[i][1]^(LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n)];
end :
end :
else
LFact := ifactors(n)[2];
for i from 1 to nops(LFact) do
if (LFact[i][1] - 1 mod p = 0) then
LD := [op(LD), LFact[i]];
end :
end :
for i from 1 to nops(LD) do
P := convert(Berlekamp(x^p - 1, x) mod LD[i][1], list);
if (P[1] - x + 1 mod LD[i][1] <> 0) then
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[1] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), ((LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[1] - x) mod n) &^(LD[i][1]^(LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n)];
else
LB := Bezout(LD[i][1], n/(LD[i][1]^LD[i][2]), P[2] - x + 1);
GEN := [op(GEN), (LD[i][1] * LB[1] - (P[2] - x) mod n) &^(LD[i][1]^(LD[i][2] - 1)) mod n)];
end :
end :
if (GEN = [ ]) then
GEN := [1];
end;
eval(GEN);
end :

```

Algorithm 2.4

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